

Mixing Deterministic and Stochastic Propagation for Assessing MmWave Small-cell Networks

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Abstract—Ray-based and hybrid propagation models are today considered as valuable solutions to fulfill 5G wireless channel modeling requirements. They are a complement or alternative to the stochastic approaches when link-level and system-level simulations deal with millimeter-wave (mmWave), ultra-dense deployment and/or large antenna arrays. The present article proposes an extension of an urban ray-based model for the assessment of a 60-GHz outdoor small-cell network. The multi-paths are predicted from interactions with the static environment, but also with randomly-positioned vehicles and user-bodies. Both the vehicles and the user-body generate ray-path blockage, and (in case of the vehicle) new propagation paths. This sometimes affects the cell selection or beam orientation, and significantly changes the received signal strength and inter-cell interference. The user-body blockage is illustrated on two simple use cases (single-cell and two-cell scenarios). Then the impact of both stochastic components is assessed through the performance simulation of a whole mmWave small-cell network.

Index Terms—millimeter-wave, ray-tracing, propagation channel model, obstructions, small-cell network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Most PHY-layer techniques designed for 3G and 4G systems have been evaluated and refined through link-level or even multi-link simulations, using stochastic propagation channel models, from the simple tapped delay line models to the MIMO-compliant geometry-based bidirectional models like the ones proposed by the European COST 273 action [1] or the WINNER projects [2][3]. The deterministic approaches, which typically rely on ray-tracing or ray-launching, were primarily devoted to network coverage predictions and network radio-planning in complex environments. Using deterministic tools in test and validation simulation frameworks was more an exception. Today there is a growing interest for the introduction of deterministic or hybrid solutions at early research and final validation stages, in particular by equipment vendors working on 5G systems with large antenna arrays or investigating the above-6GHz spectrum. There are a few reasons for this. The extension of the stochastic channel models to fulfill 5G requirements is a challenge. The fact that channel properties strongly differ between the well-known sub-6GHz frequencies and the millimeter-wave (mmWave) spectrum is one difficulty. The need for accurate spatial consistency and 3D directions in ultra-dense network simulations are two other ones. New channel measurements are required; research activity is intensive today, but such measurements and subsequent

model derivation necessarily take time. In addition, higher models complexity is expected.

Besides, the ray-based models are a mature technology, and comparisons to mmWave measurements generally show a good agreement. Deterministic propagation models usually yield a better correlation with measurements than stochastic models, especially in non line-of-sight conditions. Optimized software implementations and ever-growing computational performance (GPU, cloud) make this kind of ray-tracing solutions able to provide numerous and rapid channel realizations. A major constraint remains the use of a geographical map data to represent the main objects in the environment.

The recent METIS channel model [4] proposes a map-based approach as an alternative to stochastic models which may not be applicable in all cases. The map-based model is composed of a fully-specified geographical data (so-called Madrid grid) on which a ray-based prediction is applied. Such model can generate all large-scale and small-scale channel properties or may be used to feed a stochastic modeling with some deterministic large-scale parameters. Beside, the MiWEBA European project has recently released a channel model with hybridation of deterministic reflected paths and stochastic components [5].

The present article exploits the ray-based model described in [6] and adjusted to 60 GHz [7] to assess the performance of an outdoor mmWave small-cell network. The model is not used as it was originally. Indeed stochastic components are integrated to reproduce the high sensitivity of the multi-link propagation scenario to non-static objects, i.e. the body of the user itself and large vehicles (e.g. buses, trucks or vans) driving in the streets. The blockage of the 60-GHz wave by the human body or large vehicles strongly impacts the link quality and dominant propagation directions, leading to changes in the cell selection, beam selection, interference levels and even the connectivity rate. The general simulation framework and small-cell scenario is introduced in section II.

Blockage by a human body or group of bodies has been intensively studied by the scientific community, through measurements and simulations, into different frequency bands including mmWave [8]. The authors already proposed a hybridation between indoor ray-tracing and stochastic human-body blockage in [9] at 2 GHz; the focus was then on the impact of persons moving around the user. But the present article deals with a significantly different situation

where the blockage comes from the user-body itself. The implemented model is presented and illustrated in section III. The orientation of the user-body is randomly drawn, adding attenuation on the ray-paths arriving behind.

The obstruction by a bus was already analyzed in [7], using the same ray-tracing tool. The scenario was composed of two outdoor small-cells and several in-street users. The degradation on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) due to bus obstruction was 10 dB in average with a peak at 20 dB. A dramatic increase in the inter-cell interference levels was also observed, in the case where the interference impacted user (victim) is close to a group of users who are blocked by the bus and transferred to another cell. The deterministic channel model was obviously an asset in order to predict the correlation between multi-link blockages. The authors go one step further in the present article. Large vehicles are randomly distributed in all streets covered by a whole small-cell network, as proposed actually in the METIS map-based model [4].

The simulation of a dense mmWave outdoor small-cell deployment is reported in section IV. The same study was carried out in [7] with a static propagation environment. It is extended here based on the mixed deterministic and stochastic propagation framework. Small-cells are assumed to be installed on lampposts, with a beamforming antenna, while the pedestrian users are distributed along the sidewalks. The system-level simulations have two objectives: first, evaluate the interest of the mixed approach compared to purely static predictions; second, assess the performance of a mmWave outdoor small-cell network from consistent channel simulations.

Conclusions and perspective are given in section IV.

II. GENERAL SIMULATION FRAMEWORK AND SCENARIO

The studied small-cell network is shown in Fig. 1. It is similar to the one designed in [7] to provide seamless outdoor coverage in absence, but without considering in-street obstacles like bodies or vehicles. The network is composed of 18 small-cells operating at 60 GHz, deployed over a 0.090 km² wide area. The average inter-site distance (ISD) is 78 m, while the maximum ISD is 110 m. Each small-cell has only one sector.

The small-cells are assumed to be installed on lampposts at height 7m above the ground. They are equipped with an automatically steerable antenna. The half-power beamwidth (HPBW) is 22° with maximum gain 18.5 dBi. The radiation pattern is assumed to be perfectly shaped, i.e. without any significant side-lobe. The transmit power is adjusted such the EIRP is 40 dBm as allowed in current FCC rules.

The performance statistics are obtained from a Monte-Carlo process, where users are dropped randomly along the sidewalks with finite throughput demand. Multi-path propagation, cell selection, beam selection and interference calculations are executed at each iteration, as explained with more details in [7]. The IEEE 802.11ad link performance is considered [10].

An orientation is randomly set to each user, following a given probability density function $p(\theta)$ where θ is the angular distance between the sidewalk direction and the body-to-equipment direction. For simplicity, a uniform distribution has been considered in the present study. The user-body obstruction affects the multi-path propagation data based on the model described in section II.

Large vehicles are randomly dropped in the streets, as shown in Fig. 1 by purple rectangles. The number of vehicles has been arbitrarily fixed: 170/km². Their length is 12 m. They completely block any incident propagation path, but they also produce new reflections and diffractions. Metallic material is considered.

Fig. 1. Small-cell deployment (red dots) and target user locations (blue lines). The study area is 300 m x 300 m wide.

Fig. 2. Evolution of the Power angle channel spectrum.

Fig. 2 illustrates how the introduction of the user-body and large vehicles affect the predicted channel. The plotted map represents the channel power distribution versus the angle at the user antenna and delay, for the user located on the blue star in Fig. 1 and oriented in direction 248° .

Other simulation parameters are reported in Table I.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS.

System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PHY waveform: Single-Carrier (SC) - Central frequency: 60 GHz - Bandwidth: 200 MHz - Mapping table: from IEEE 802.11ad, with 12 adaptive modulation schemes (MCS) - PHY net data rate: 43.8 to 525.0 Mbps
Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Noise figure: 7 dB - Antenna: omni-directional, 5 dBi - Demand: 5 Mbps - Active user density: 1000 users/km²
Power budget	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impairment loss: 8 dB - DL Rx sensitivity: -79 to -64 dBm
Simulation parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monte-Carlo: 30 iterations - Traffic: Non full-buffer

III. USER-BODY OBSTRUCTION

A. Single-user obstruction model

The Knife Edge Diffraction (KED) models have been widely used in literature to calculate the loss due to human body obstruction [4][8]. And the double knife-edge model (DKED) is found very representative of the reality. It has been proposed in the METIS model [4] to consider the human body as an infinitely long screen with two edges.

However, the knife edge model underestimates the shadowing when the antenna is close to the obstructing body. A more appropriate approach is to consider the human body as a cylinder with uniform dielectric properties. At 60 GHz frequency, the electrical size of the human body is relatively large and the body must be considered as a rounded obstacle instead of a sharp edge. Then the Uniform Theory of Diffraction (UTD) for rounded objects or the rounded edge model by ITU-526 [11] can apply. In particular, the UTD-based creeping wave model- was shown to perform well as compared to the exact solution [12], and is proposed for on-body channel predictions.

For implementation simplicity, we have chosen the [11] formulation for our model. An extra attenuation due to a curved obstacle is added to the KED loss. The relevance of this model is well-known for large range propagation, but we decided to evaluate its accuracy for the short-range obstruction that is considered here. It is compared to the creeping wave model results published in [12]. In this article, the human body is modelled as a cylinder of radius $r=0.2\text{m}$. Omni-directional antenna is considered for the receiver which is at a distance $d=0.205\text{m}$ from the centre of

the cylinder. The receiver is oriented at different angles ϕ as shown in Fig 3. Frequency is 60 GHz. The obstruction loss from the single knife-edge, creeping wave, and the ITU-526 rounded edge models are plotted together in Fig. 4, showing good agreement between the two latter ones, and strong underestimation from the first one. Note the creeping wave model predictions on this scenario have been validated against measurements [12].

In the proposed implementation here, the body orientation is random and the distance between the body centre and the antenna is $d=0.4\text{m}$. In this situation, and if we assume the base station is far away from the user, the shadow region is 60° wide, thus covering 16.7% of the plane.

We decided to consider only one diffracted edge instead of two. The loss in the shadowed area where both diffracted paths are of same order is very strong and the improved accuracy offered by the double-edge approach will not have any impact on the simulations.

The red plot in Fig. 4 illustrates the loss that is computed in the remaining of our study, i.e. with $d=0.4\text{m}$.

Fig. 3. Shadow region caused by the user-body; Antenna distribution considered in the analysis is represented by blue dots.

Fig. 4. Obstruction loss from the user-body.

B. Single-cell simulation

The impact of user-body obstruction is first evaluated in a single-cell scenario. One of the small-cells shown in Fig. 1 has been chosen and users were dropped on the sidewalks 40 m around. Fig. 5 shows the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) with and without the impact of user-body obstruction. The users suffer a significant degradation; the average SNR reduces by 1.7 dB and the 10% percentile decreases by 3.5 dB. However the impact is very small for the highest percentiles; the SNR reduces by only 0.3 dB at the 90% percentile.

Fig. 5. Single-cell scenario: CDF of SNR.

Fig. 6. Two-cell scenario: CDF of Inter-cell Interference levels.

Fig. 7. Two-cell scenario: CDF of SINR.

C. Two-cells simulation

The previous scenario is extended to the case of a street containing two small-cells separated by 80m. The purpose is to assess the impact of user-body obstruction on inter-cell interference and user performance. Twenty users in average are dropped at each Monte-Carlo iteration into the portion of the street located between the small-cells. Note there is no outage in absence of user-body obstruction.

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the CDF of respectively the inter-cell interference levels and the signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR), with and without user-body consideration. The user-body obstruction leads to lower interference levels. The median interference reduces significantly by 6.7 dB while the most critical interference levels (at highest percentiles) exhibits lower variations; i.e. 0.6 dB at the 90% percentile and lower than 0.1 dB at the 95% percentile.

The SINR CDF exhibits degradation caused by the signal reduction such as observed in the previous single cell scenario; the SINR reduces by 2.9 dB and 0.5 dB for respectively the 10% and 50% percentiles. But there is insignificant degradation for the 90% percentile. The impact of the body obstruction has been partly mitigated via two mechanisms: 1) a strong SNR reduction leads the user to switch to the other cell; 2) when interference is greater or similar to the noise level (which is generally the case here), the reduction of the interference levels may compensate part of the signal decrease. This is particularly true for users for which the body severely obstructs the closest small-cell; those users move to the other cell providing lower signal strength; but then the interference that is coming from the closest cell is negligible. Finally, the simulation results indicate that a major effect of the user-body obstruction is higher inter-cell isolation.

The basic studies presented in this section III were chosen to properly validate, illustrate and make understandable the user performance evolutions. Section IV deals with a more complex scenario.

IV. SMALL-CELL NETWORK PERFORMANCE

The effect of the user-body blockage and interactions with large vehicles is now assessed through the whole network of small-cells scenario. The density of active user s is 1000 users/km², meaning that 90 users in average are dropped at each iteration.

The network performance is computed in three different scenarios: 1) no stochastic component; 2) consideration of the user-body obstruction; 3) consideration of both user-body and vehicles together. The results for respectively the Inter-cell interference and the SINR are given in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.

The reduction of the inter-cell interference due to the user-body blockage is confirmed in Fig. 8, with an average decrease of 1.9 dB. As observed in the two-cell scenario, this positive effect, as well as the optimal cell selection process we consider in the simulation, makes the SINR degradation quite limited. As illustrated in Fig. 9, the 10% SINR percentile decreases by 1.1 dB while the median

SINR decreases by 0.2 dB due to body obstruction. Adding the vehicle obstruction has an insignificant impact on link quality. Actually the impact of vehicle obstruction is local only and has been compensated by two mechanisms (the same as for the body obstruction but at a higher degree): 1) The obstruction of the dominant path can be partly mitigated by the system by pointing the antenna towards another path; 2) The reduction of the SINR leads the user to switch to the other cell and benefit from significant interference reductions due to vehicle obstruction. This latter mechanism is emphasized in the streets where small-cells are distributed alternatively along each sides of the street. Remark that as observed in the single bus obstruction scenario investigated in [7], there are some specific cases where interferences may dramatically increase but their occurrence appears to be small. The SINR improvement at highest percentiles that was observed in the two-cell scenario is no more visible when assessing the performance of a larger network.

Fig. 8. Whole network scenario: CDF of Inter-cell Interference level.

Fig. 9. Whole network scenario: CDF of SINR.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVE

A ray-based channel model is applied on a geographical map data enriched with random non-static objects. The goal is to produce realistic channel realizations in the context of a dense outdoor 60-GHz small-cell network evaluation. The presented study illustrates the impact of random large

vehicles and randomly-oriented user-bodies into different scenarios.

The user-body is shown to sometimes bring positive effect, with stronger inter-cell isolation. Besides, the degradation on the useful signal strength is not affecting too much the global network performance, as soon as the victim users can switch to another cell with no body masking. The obstruction by the user-body and vehicles finally leads to a quite limited reduction of the SINR. Significant degradation occurs only on the very worse-served users: 1.1 dB on the 10% percentile; and 0.2 dB on the median percentile. Analysis will continue in future studies in order to better identify, understand and model the main non-static factors that should be considered in mmWave network design.

Hybridizing ray-based models with stochastic components is at an early stage. The propagation framework should later be extended with interactions on other bodies and in-street objects. Adding the dynamic dimension (i.e. time variant channel and network scheduling) is also a major perspective.

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